

THE EFFECT OF PRESSURE ON THERMAL AGING OF A GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITE

H. Thomas Hahn and Joseph I. Lee

Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering Department

University of California, Los Angeles

Los Angeles, CA 90025-1597, USA

SUMMARY: The effect of air pressure on thermal aging has been investigated by exposing AS4/3501-6 [$\pm 45^\circ$]_{2s} graphite/epoxy composite to a temperature of 121°C at four different air pressures. The weight loss, tensile strength, and elastic modulus were measured to determine the extent of degradation. The respective degradation rates remained fairly constant over the aging time and were highly dependent on the air pressure exposed. Analytical models were developed to describe the observed degradation of these three properties. These models could be used to design accelerated thermal aging based on air pressure.

KEYWORDS: thermal aging, pressure effect, graphite/epoxy composite

INTRODUCTION

Thermal aging of polymer matrix composites has been studied by a number of researchers. Using a quasi-isotropic graphite/epoxy laminate, Greer [1] showed that the tensile, compressive, shear, and flexural properties decreased substantially after 3000 hours of aging at a temperature of 177°C (350°F). After 6000 hours, the laminate was declared useless with property losses as high as 70% of their original values.

Bowles, Jayn and Leonhardt [2] studied the thermo-oxidative stability (TOS) of a high-temperature resin PMR-15 by aging it in air at temperatures of 288, 316, and 343°C. Optical and electron microscopy observations revealed an onset of a thin layer of degradation at the surface due to aging. This layer grew with increasing aging time. Surface cracking was also found while the core was left free of oxidative degradation. Similar results were obtained by Nam and Seferis [3] on bismaleimide/carbon fiber composites. While the core was relatively protected from aging, microscopic degradation increased slowly with prolonged time.

Traditionally, weight loss measurements have been used to determine degradation. However, they may not be a good indicator because of the two competing mechanisms: reaction kinetics and mass transfer [4]. The latter mechanism can result in a weight gain albeit minute. Flynn and Wall [5] and Lee and Levi [6] used a thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) on small specimens to determine the reaction kinetics and activation energies. However, Arnold et al. [7] and MacCallum [8] pointed out the unreliability of the results from TGA alone. Nevertheless, a substantial weight loss is a clear indication of material degradation.

Although specifics of thermo-oxidative degradation process are not well known, it does involve the influence of oxygen. An experiment by Ciutacu, Budrugaec, and Niculae [9] showed that thermal degradation of a glass/epoxy composite was accelerated under high oxygen pressure. Thus it is plausible that higher oxygen content through a higher air pressure could accelerate the aging process and lead to a shorter testing time.

Although increasing the pressure can accelerate the thermal aging process, temperature effects themselves are also important. Experiments must be conducted below the glass transition temperature T_g of the matrix resin to avoid any nonlinear effects and anomalous degradation [10-12]. Experiments performed below T_g helps to achieve test conditions similar, if not exactly equal, to the actual environment. Since each material has a different T_g , it is important to tailor each experiment accordingly. This way, lifetimes of polymeric composites can be estimated with greater accuracy.

Experimental data showing a significant effect of air pressure on thermal aging in graphite/epoxy composites were reported by Tsotsis et al. [13]. The present paper proposes analytical models to describe the observed degradation behavior macroscopically. The models can be used to design accelerated thermal aging based on air pressure.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

To highlight the matrix-dominated properties, $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2s}$ angle-ply laminates were fabricated from AS3/3501-6 prepreg following the manufacturer's cure cycle. The laminates were then cut into coupons 254 mm long \times 25.4 mm wide, as per the ASTM D3039. The average thickness was 1.016 mm.

The test chamber consisted of four pressure vessels placed in an oven maintained at a constant temperature of 121°C. The test temperature was kept below the glass transition temperature of the composite to avoid any nonlinear effects. Each pressure vessel was regulated to maintain a specific pressure: 0.101 Mpa (ambient), 0.345 MPa, 1.03 MPa, and 1.72 MPa. Since the goal was to accelerate thermal aging by increasing pressure, low pressures were not used.

Twenty-five specimens were placed in each pressure chamber for a total of 100 specimens. They were placed on a rack to allow air to flow around each specimen.

The total testing time of 5000 hr comprised five cycles with each cycle being 1000 hr long. At the end of each cycle, all specimens were taken out of the chamber for weighing and 5 specimens from each vessel were tested in uniaxial tension. Therefore, 20 specimens were tested at the conclusion of each cycle. Some specimens were prepared for optical microscopy. Mechanical testing was conducted on an Instron Model 4483 machine as per the ASTM D3039. Further details may be found in [13].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The average weight of all specimens was 9.90 g with a coefficient of variation of 1.5%. The weight change of each specimen during thermal aging is shown in Fig. 1 and the calculated weight losses are shown in Fig. 2. After 1000 hr at the ambient pressure $p_o=0.101$ MPa and $p/p_o=3.4$, respectively, some specimens show a slight weight gain as a result of oxygen uptake in the surfaces. The weight gain is more prominent at the latter pressure. With increasing aging time and pressure, however, all specimens lose weight and the rate of weight loss increases with increasing pressure.

A fairly good correlation is observed between initial weights and 3000-hr weight losses at the two highest pressures, Fig. 3. The corresponding correlation coefficients are 0.75 and 0.86, respectively, with the larger value for the highest pressure. The initial weight also correlates with the initial thickness (coefficient = 0.68), Fig. 4. Thus it is believed that a larger weight is the result of higher matrix content and a larger surface area, and is expected to yield a larger weight loss.

that a larger weight is the result of higher matrix content and a larger surface area, and is expected to yield a larger weight loss.

Fig. 3. Correlations between weight loss and initial weight at 3000 hr

Fig. 4. Correlation between initial weight and thickness

The strength and modulus losses due to thermo-oxidative aging are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. Both losses increase with increasing weight loss, Fig. 7. The calculated correlation coefficients are 0.90 for both cases. Similarly to the weight gain observed after 1000 hr, the modulus also increases slightly at the ambient pressure. Such increase is believed to be the result of additional cross-linking occurring at the test temperature.

During thermal aging both cross-linking and chain scission occur [15]. The additional cross-linking causes the polymer matrix to become more brittle and stiffer, and to shrink. The chain scission breaks the polymer chains resulting in microcracks. Residual stresses resulting from cure shrinkage enhances microcracking and help these microcracks grow. With more oxygen present, this thermo-oxidative degradation process is accelerated.

The strength loss (maximum of 70%) is much more severe than the modulus loss (maximum of 44%). The reason is that the chain scission degrades the strength much more than the modulus and the polymer becomes stiffer due to the additional cross-linking. The chain scission starts from the exposed surfaces and moves inward and results in loss of material.

Fig. 5. Strength loss due to thermal aging

Fig. 6. Modulus loss due to thermal aging

Fig. 7. Strength and modulus losses correlated with weight loss

The cross-section of an unaged specimen does not show any damage, as expected, Fig. 8(a). However, a specimen aged for 5000 hr at 1.72 MPa shows extensive amounts of delamination, fiber separation, and matrix loss, Fig. 8(b). Damage decreases toward the center of the laminate on the left side. The free surface is on the right side where the matrix material has disappeared leaving many fibers isolated.

Fig. 8. Photomicrographs of cross sections

ANALYTICAL MODELING

The thermo-oxidative degradation described in the preceding section can be modeled as proposed in [9]. The analytical model starts with the following kinetic equation for the reduction of, e.g., weight w [16, 17]:

$$\frac{dw}{dt} = -k_w w^a \quad (1)$$

where t is aging time, k_w is a rate constant, and a is the overall order of the degradation process. Since the data in Fig. 2 show a fairly linear relationship between weight loss and aging time, a is taken to be zero and Eq. (1) reduces to

$$\frac{dw}{dt} = -k_w \quad (2)$$

As temperature is kept constant, the rate constant k_w is a function of pressure only. With a power relationship for k_w [9], i.e.,

$$k_w = \mathbf{b}_w (p/p_o)^{n_w} t, \quad p_o = 0.101 \text{ MPa (ambient pressure)} \quad (3)$$

where p is pressure and n_w is a constant, the final equation for weight loss becomes

$$w = w_o - \mathbf{b}_w (p/p_o)^{n_w} t \quad (4)$$

Here w_o is the initial weight and \mathbf{b}_w represents the rate of weight loss at the ambient pressure.

The data for strength \mathbf{S} and modulus E in Figs. 5 and 6, respectively, indicate that similar equations can be used to describe their degradation:

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S}_o - \mathbf{b}_s (p/p_o)^{n_s} t \quad (5)$$

$$E = E_o - \mathbf{b}_e (p/p_o)^{n_e} t \quad (6)$$

The constants \mathbf{b} and n were determined from the property loss data shown in Figs. 2, 5 and 6 using the linear least-squares method. The results are listed in Table 1. The least-squares slope of the modulus data was slightly positive at the ambient pressure indicating a modulus increase. However, this was not taken into account in the determination of the constants.

Table 1. Degradation constants

Constant	Weight	Strength	Modulus
Loss rate at amb. Press. \mathbf{b}	2.11×10^{-3} mg/hr	2.73×10^{-3} MPa/hr	0.152×10^{-3} Gpa/hr
Exponent n	0.791	0.761	0.833

Predictions of Eqs. (4)–(6) are compared with the experimental data in Figs. 2, 5 and 6. For their simplicity, the models show a fairly good correlation with the data.

CONCLUSIONS

The thermo-oxidative degradation of AS4/3501 graphite/epoxy composite at 121°C is accelerated by air pressure. A 5000-hr aging at a pressure 17 times the ambient pressure can reduce the matrix-controlled strength by as much as 70% coupled with a weight loss of 11%. Although smaller, the corresponding modulus reduction is also quite significant at 44%. Such severe material degradation at high pressure is in good contrast to the negligible property changes observed under the ambient pressure. The weight loss correlates well with the strength and modulus losses, indicating that the material loss is responsible for some of these reductions.

Variations in initial weight tend to translate into variations in properties in such a way that heavier specimens lose more weight and hence more strength and modulus. The reason is that heavier specimens have more matrix material to lose and larger surface areas exposed to the environment.

The observed damages are in the form of microcracking, fiber separation, delamination, and matrix material loss. The degradation mechanism is chain scission which is enhanced by the presence of oxygen. The degradation starts from exposed surfaces and moves inward. The first sign of damage occurs at the interface between plies. Once delamination occurs, oxygen can enter through the ply interfaces to attack the interior of plies. Ply cracks then begin to nucleate and grow eventually breaking plies into pieces.

Analytical models have been developed to account for the effect of pressure on the observed property degradation. The models are based on the observation that the property reduction rates are independent of time and assume a power law dependency on pressure. They show a fairly good correlation with the experimental data.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This paper is based on work performed partially under a contract from The Boeing Company. The authors would like to thank Thomas K. Tsotsis for his support of the work.

REFERENCES

1. Greer, R. H., "Thermal Aging of Contemporary Graphite/Epoxy Materials," *Nat. SAMPE Symp. Exhib. Proc.*, Book 2, Covina, CA, 1979, pp. 1039-1052.
2. Bowles, K. J., Jayne, D. and Leonhardt, T. A., "Isothermal Aging Effects on PMR-15 Resin," *SAMPE Quarterly*, 1993, Vol. 24, pp. 2-9.
3. Nam, J. D. and Seferis, J. C., "Anisotropic Thermo-oxidative Stability of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymeric Composites," *SAMPE Quarterly*, 1992, Vol. 24, pp. 10-18.
4. Tsotsis T. K., "Thermo-Oxidative Aging of Composite Materials," *J. Comp. Mat.*, 1995, Vol. 29, pp. 410-422.
5. Flynn, J. H. and Wall, L. A., "A Quick Direct Method for the Determination of Activation Energy from Thermogravimetric Data," *Polym. Lett.*, Vol. 4, pp. 323-328.
6. Lee, H. T. and Levi, D. W., "Effect of Curing Temperature on the Thermal Degradation of an Epoxide Resin," *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1969, Vol. 13, pp. 1703-1709.
7. Arnold, M., Veress, G. E., Paulik, J., and Paulik, F., "Problems of Characterization of Thermoanalytical Processes by Kinetic Parameters, Part I," *J. Therm. Anal.*, Vol. 17, pp. 507-528.
8. MacCallum J. R., "Thermogravimetric Analysis of Polymers for Assessing Thermal Degradation," *Thermo. Chim. Acta*, 1985, Vol. 96, pp. 275-281.
9. Ciutacu, S., Budrugaec, P. and Niculae, I., "Accelerated Thermal Aging of Glass-Reinforced Epoxy Resin Under Oxygen Pressure," *Poly. Degrad. and Stab.* 1991, Vol. 31, pp. 365-372.
10. Tsotsis, T. K. and Lee, S. M., "Long-Term Thermo-Oxidative Aging in Composite Materials: Failure Mechanisms," *Comp. Sci. and Tech.* 1998, Vol. 58, pp. 355-368.
11. Tsotsis, T. K., Keller, S., Lee, K., Bardis, J., and Bish, J., "3000 Hours Aging of Polymeric Composite Specimens Under Elevated Pressure and Temperature," 44th International SAMPE Symposium, May 1999.
12. Tsotsis, T. K., "Long-Term Thermo-Oxidative Aging of Composites Materials: Experimental Methods," *J. Comp. Mat.*, 1998, Vol. 32, pp. 1115-1135.
13. Tsotsis, T. K., Keller, S., Lee, K., Bardis, J., and Bish, J., "Aging of Polymeric Composite Specimens for 5000 Hours at Elevated Pressure and Temperature," *Comp. Sci. and Tech.* 2001, Vol. 61, pp. 75-86.
14. Grassie, N., Scott, G., *Polymer Degradation and Stabilisation*, Cambridge University Press, New York, 1985.
15. Emanuel, N. M., Buchachenko, A. L., *Chemical Physics of Polymer Degradation and Stabilization*, VNU Science Press, Netherlands, 1987.
16. Dakin, T. W., "Electrical Insulation Deterioration," *Electro-Technology*, 1960, 66, p. 123.

17. Dakin, T. W., "Electrical Insulation Deterioration Treated as a Chemical Chemical Rate Phenomenon," *Transactions of AIEE*, 1948, Vol. 67, p. 113.